

TABLE I

System	$E_{1/2}$ in volt vs S.C.E. (at 25°)	αn (at 25°)	$id/h_{1/2}$ ($\mu\text{amp cm}^{-1/2}$)	Activation Energy of Diffusion [Kcal]	Diffusion Current Constant (at 25°)	Diffusion Coefficient (at 25°) $\times 10^5$
Ethanolamine (1.0 M) NaOH (0.1 M)						
No ligand	-0.489	0.9456	0.570	3.76	2.52	1.933
Monoethanolamine	-0.489	0.8628	0.489	3.80	2.16	1.704
Diethanolamine	-0.499	0.8756	0.422	5.54	1.96	1.347
N-methyl diethanolamine	-0.511	0.9234	0.366	5.66	1.63	0.813
Triethanolamine	-0.519	0.9234	0.340	7.38	1.50	0.721

It appears from the half-wave potential values that MEA does not form any complex with Tl(I) whereas appreciable complex formation takes place with DEA, MDEA and TEA. With a view to study the relative complexing ability of different ethanolamines, polarograms were recorded with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Tl(I), 0.1M NaOH and varying concentrations of the ligands. It has been observed that except with MEA, both the half-wave potentials and the diffusion currents progressively decreased with the increase of ligand concentration. In case of MEA, only the diffusion current decreased slightly with increasing ligand concentration. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ for DEA and MDEA systems were marginal. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs logarithm of TEA concentrations was linear which indicated the presence of a single complex species in solution.

For a sufficiently weak complex of the type ML_x , the diffusion current (i_d) for the reduction of M can be related with the ligand concentration (C_L) by the following expression,

$$i_d^{-1} = K^{-1} \cdot a^{-1} + k(K \cdot a)^{-1} C_L^x$$

where,

K = diffusion current per unit concentration of the depolarizer.

k = stability constant of the complex.

C_L = total ligand concentration.

a = concentration of M.

x = number of ligands per metal ion.

The plot of $1/i_d$ vs concentration of ethanolamines (C_L) for 1.0 mM Tl (I) polarographed under identical

condition is shown in the figure. The virtually horizontal curve for MEA-system indicates that no complex formation takes place. The initial slight rise may be attributed to the slight change of the supporting electrolyte due to the change of MEA concentration and the effect is imperceptible at higher ligand concentrations. The linear curves with gradually increasing slopes for the DEA, MDEA and TEA systems show that ML type complexes having $x=1$ are formed in solution. The stability order is $TEA > MDEA > DEA$, the slopes being proportional to the stability constants. The results are in agreement with the shifts of the $E_{1/2}$ values of Tl (I) in presence of these ligands.

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Mercury(II) Complexes with Substituted Thiourea

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SEVERAL complexes of zinc (II), cadmium (II) and mercury (II) with thiourea have been reported¹⁻³ earlier. Since comparatively less number of mercury (II) complexes are known, it was thought worthwhile to study the complexes of mercury(II) with some substituted thiourea and the present investigation reports seven compounds of mercury (II) having the composition $[Hg L Cl_2]$, where L is N-methyl, N,N'-diethyl, N-allyl, o-tolyl, p-tolyl, N-phenyl and N,N'-diphenyl thiourea.

Experimental :

Aqueous solution of mercury (II) chloride was reacted with ethanolic solution of different substituted thiourea in 1:2 ratio. Some of the halide complexes appear immediately after vigorous shaking. A few of the complexes were formed after keeping the mixture standing for some hours. The precipitated compounds are suction filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. The composition of the complexes are determined by estimating metal, halogen and sulfur by standard methods. Conductance was measured in 0.001M acetone solution using a Toshniwal

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, M. P. AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF Hg(II) COMPLEXES

Compounds	M.P. (°C.)	Cond. (mhos/ Cm ² .)	% Hg		% Halogen		% Sulfur	
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
HgCl ₂ (N.Me.tu)	184	21.2	55.12	56.40	19.26	19.67	8.70	8.86
HgCl ₂ (N.Ph.tu)	250	25.8	47.08	47.29	16.53	16.79	7.09	7.56
HgCl ₂ (N,N'-di.Et.tu)	199	15.5	49.26	49.73	17.19	17.62	7.90	7.92
HgCl ₂ (N-allyl.tu)	185	20.5	51.35	51.68	18.06	18.35	8.06	8.27
HgCl ₂ (di.ph.tu)	250	20.8	39.96	40.07	13.98	14.23	6.24	6.41
HgCl ₂ (o-tolyl.tu)	250	12.5	45.61	45.76	15.92	16.25	6.98	7.32
HgCl ₂ (p-Tolyl.tu)	250	18.3	45.35	45.76	16.06	16.25	7.04	7.32

TABLE 2—Infrared spectra (Cm⁻¹)

Compound	ν (C-S)	N-C-N bend and ν (C-S)	NH ₂ (A ₁) rocking N-C-N bend and ν (C-S)	(B ₁) N-C-N stretch	NH ₂ ⁺ bend- ing	ν (N-H)
N.Me.tu.	740 s	1085	1420	1475	1615	3200 s
N,N'-Di.Et.tu	740 s	1080	1425	1480	1620	3220 s
N-allyl.tu.	725 s	1090	1420	1485	1615	3220 s
o-Tolyl.tu.	765 s	1095	1430	1475	1625	3200 s
p-Tolyl.tu.	730 s	1080	1425	1485	1620	3230 s
N.Ph.tu.	755 s	1085	1430	1490	1625	3250 s
Di.Ph.tu.	760 s	1085	1430	1490	1625	3250 s
HgCl ₂ (N.Me.tu)	720 s	1100	1410	1490	1620	3200 s
HgCl ₂ (N,N Di.Et.tu)	730 s	1090	1420	1485	1625	2190 s
HgCl ₂ (N.allyl.tu)	710 s	1100	1415	1490	1630	3190 s
HgCl ₂ (o-tolyl.tu)	730 g	1110	1410	1495	1625	3180 s
HgCl ₂ (p-tolyl.tu)	710 s	1090	1410	1500	1630	3200 s
HgCl ₂ (N.Ph.tu.)	625 s	1100	1420	1805	1635	3200 s
HgCl ₂ (di.ph.tu)	730 s	1110	1420	1500	1635	3200 s

conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a Unicam Sp-200 spectrophotometer. The relevant analytical, m. p. and conductance data are recorded in Table 1 and the infrared spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion :

The halide complexes reported in the present investigation are all white amorphous compounds of the composition [Hg L Cl₂] as reflected from their analysis. These are sparingly soluble in organic solvents and have high melting points. All these compounds are electrolytes as the Δ_M values in acetone (*M*/1000 solution) is very low being of the order of 12-25 mhos/cm². Though direct evidence for the metal-ligand bonding could not be obtained as it was beyond the range of spectrophotometer used, the ligand absorption bands are modified indicating bonding to the metal ion. As the analysis of the complexes indicate the coordination of one ligand molecule they are apparently three coordinated.

The infrared spectra of all the complexes with substituted thiourea follow a general pattern of mercury (II) thiourea complexes and a detailed discussion in this connection will be desirable. The absorption bands of the ligands and the complexes with their assignment⁵ are recorded in Table 2. The high frequency N-H absorption bands in the spectrum of substituted thiourea are not shifted much to lower frequencies indicating that nitrogen to metal bonds are not present⁶. The sharp bands observed in the region ~3200 Cm⁻¹ are undoubtedly assigned to the N-H stretching vibration and that around ~1600 Cm⁻¹ correspond to the bands of thiourea of almost the same frequency and can be assigned to the NH₂ bending vibration. Bands about ~1500 Cm⁻¹ are attributable to N-C-N stretching vibration

of the B₁ type and that about ~1400 Cm⁻¹ correspond to the (A₁) band of thiourea assigned to NH₂ vibrations, N-C-N and C-S stretching vibrations. The bands observed around ~1100 Cm⁻¹ are attributed to N-C-N bending and C-S stretching vibration of thiourea. C-S stretching vibrations appear in the ~730 Cm⁻¹ region of the spectrum. The absorption bands in the spectra of metal thiourea complexes which have been assigned to the particular vibrations noted above indicate the presence of sulfur to metal bonds in these complexes.

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